

THE ACCUMULATION OF DAMAGE IN WOVEN CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES UNDER QUASI-STATIC TENSILE LOADING

Kane Ironside, Paul Smith, Julie Yeomans
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
University of Surrey
Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH United Kingdom

Mike Percival
Composites Group, Rolls-Royce plc
Derby DE24 8BJ United Kingdom

ABSTRACT

The behaviours of woven SiC fibre reinforced Pyrex and calcium aluminosilicate (CAS) matrix composites under quasi-static tensile loading have been studied. Both systems show an initial linear elastic region on the stress-strain curve with departure from linearity occurring between 0.04 and 0.06 % applied strain. Unloading of the laminates from higher strains and subsequent reloading showed hysteretic behaviour as well as a reduction in stiffness, indicating matrix cracking damage. An edge replication technique has been used to study and quantify the matrix micro-cracking and to produce plots of stiffness reduction as a function of crack density.

INTRODUCTION

The majority of the work in the literature concerned with woven fibre composites has, until recently, concentrated on the behaviour of polymer matrix systems. In particular the elastic properties of woven materials have been modelled, e.g. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5], and there is increasing interest in the topic of damage development and residual properties. Some of the perceived advantages of woven composites compared to non-woven composites (in particular processability) are also of interest to potential users of ceramic composites. Hence there is now published work on the mechanical behaviour of woven ceramic matrix composites (CMCs), in particular woven CMCs produced by chemical vapour deposition and chemical vapour infiltration, e.g. [6, 7]. At present there appears to be little published literature on the mechanical behaviour of woven glass-ceramic matrix composites (GCMCs) although much work has been published on the behaviour of non-woven GCMCs, e.g. [8, 9, 10]. The present paper presents results concerning the mechanical behaviour of woven SiC/Pyrex and SiC/CAS composites of various weave architectures.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Woven SiC fibre reinforced Pyrex (SiC/Pyrex) laminates, of plain weave and five-harness satin type, and woven SiC fibre reinforced calcium aluminosilicate (SiC/CAS) laminates, of plain weave and eight harness satin type, were supplied by Rolls-Royce plc. The laminates were cut into test coupons 100 mm by 15 mm and the edges were polished to a 1 μm finish using conventional metallographic grinding and polishing techniques. Aluminium end tabs were then bonded to the test coupons with the coupons having a final gauge length of 50 mm.

The test coupons were tested in an Instron 1175 tensile testing machine using a 100 kN load cell, at a crosshead speed of 0.05 mm/min for all the tests reported here. A strain gauge and/or an extensometer were used to measure the applied strain during the test. Strain gauges were processed using a digital strain indicator (Measurements Group P-3500), with the load and strain results recorded using a pen chart recorder. The strain measured by the extensometer was processed by the strain data unit of the Instron 1175. The values of the modulus were calculated from the 0.04 % secant modulus of the loading curve.

Both continuous and discontinuous tensile tests were used to study the mechanical behaviour of the woven material systems. In the continuous loading tests the test coupons were loaded without interruption until catastrophic failure occurred. With the discontinuous tests the test coupon was loaded to a known applied strain, then unloaded to zero load (at which point there was an associated residual strain), and then reloaded to a higher applied strain. Some cyclic tests were also carried out, in which the loading/unloading regime is repeated a number of times to a constant applied strain.

Acetate replicas of the test coupon edge were taken while the coupon was under load. From the edge replicas a matrix micro-cracking density, expressed as total crack length per unit area of edge section, could be calculated.

RESULTS

SiC/PYREX

Fig. 1 shows the internal structure of an as-received plain weave (PW) SiC/Pyrex laminate in a plane parallel to the warp tows. The figure shows the warp fibre tows (longitudinal) and the weft fibre tows (transverse). From the figure the undulation of the warp fibres as they pass under and then over the weft fibres is seen clearly as is the overall quality of the material, which shows little porosity. It can also be seen that the composite contains a significant fraction of matrix-rich material in addition to the longitudinal and transverse tows.

Table 1 shows the basic mechanical properties for SiC/Pyrex under quasi-static tensile loading i.e. the mean Young's modulus with standard deviation, the Poisson's ratio, ν_{xy} ; the stress, σ_f , and strain, ϵ_f , to catastrophic failure.

Fig. 2 shows a typical stress-strain curve for a PW SiC/Pyrex composite loaded continuously in quasi-static tension. The curve deviates from the initial linear elastic region between an applied strain of 0.04 - 0.06 %. From the discontinuous quasi-static

tensile tests the reduced elastic stiffness and the crack density were determined. Fig. 3 shows the reduced stiffness as a function of applied strain for a PW SiC/Pyrex composite. Fig. 4 shows the reduced stiffness and matrix crack density as functions of applied strain for a five harness satin weave (5HSW) SiC/Pyrex composite. As indicated earlier, the crack density data were obtained from edge replicas. By comparing the replica with a photomicrograph of the laminate edge, it was established that the matrix cracking is present in the transverse tows, the matrix-rich regions and, to a lesser extent, in the longitudinal tows.

SiC/CAS

Fig. 5 shows the internal structure of an as-received plain weave SiC/CAS laminate in a plane parallel to the warp tows. There was evidence of some porosity in the CAS matrix laminates.

Table 2 summarises the basic data from the tensile tests carried out on the SiC/CAS materials.

Figs. 6 and 7 show the reduced stiffness and matrix micro-crack density of a PW SiC/CAS composite and an eight harness satin weave (8HSW) SiC/CAS composite, respectively, as functions of applied strain. The trends of the data for the two weaves are similar. Comparable edge crack density measurements and stiffness reductions are seen.

DISCUSSION

SiC/PYREX

The continuously loaded stress-strain curves show a linear elastic region, from which the elastic modulus can be determined. In Table 1 it is seen that the initial moduli for the 5HSW laminates are sometimes lower than those for the PW laminates when they would be expected to be higher, due to fibres undulating less in 5HSW. This is believed to be a consequence of a lower fibre volume fraction in the 5HSW laminates. The "knee" or deviation from the linear region occurs between an applied strain of 0.04 - 0.06% and is a result of matrix micro-cracking. Continued loading causes further matrix micro-cracking and subsequent 0° fibre failures, until catastrophic failure.

In some of the discontinuous cyclic loading tests, the strain (and hence modulus) data obtained using the strain gauge and extensometer were compared. For some samples the modulus values calculated from the strain gauge were slightly higher than the values calculated from the extensometer. Two possible reasons for this are the effect of any strain gauge misalignment (which will lower the measured strain) and that the strain gauge may cause localised stiffening of the sample, especially in the presence of matrix micro-cracking. Overall however, there was good agreement between the moduli values calculated from the strain gauge and extensometer, especially when compared on a normalised basis, and similar hysteretic behaviour was observed. In particular in cyclic loading tensile tests it was found that the hysteresis loops closed after approximately three or four cycles, depending on the loading history of the test coupon. Such hysteresis behaviour is similar to that seen in earlier work on non-woven laminates [10] and is believed to be associated with internal friction, such as that arising from fibre/matrix sliding.

SiC/CAS

As in the SiC/Pyrex composite the continuously loaded stress-strain curve for a SiC/CAS composite shows a linear elastic region, with the knee occurring between 0.04 - 0.06% applied strain. The initial moduli for the satin weave coupons were higher than those from the plain weave coupons, which is as expected. The trends of the relative values of the moduli from extensometer and strain gauge were similar to those seen in the SiC/Pyrex laminates. Similar hysteretic behaviour was seen also between the two systems, with the hysteresis loops in the CAS matrix laminates closing after two or three cycles, depending on the loading history of the test coupon.

The matrix micro-cracking behaviour and associated modulus reduction is quite similar between the PW and 8HSW SiC/CAS systems. Figs. 6 and 7 show that the matrix micro-cracking starts at an applied strain of 0.04 %, and further applied strain increases the cracking density to a value of approximately 2 mm^{-1} with a modulus reduction of about 50 %. The behaviour is also similar to that seen in SiC/Pyrex.

CONCLUSION

An initial linear elastic region is seen in the stress-strain curves of both SiC/Pyrex and SiC/CAS woven composites. Beyond the elastic region the modulus decreases as a consequence of matrix micro-cracking. A comparison of the modulus and other features of the stress/strain behaviour calculated using the applied strain measured by a strain gauge and extensometer show little difference. The reduced stiffness has been correlated with the crack density by measuring the latter using an edge replication technique. Current work is directed towards modelling this data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank EPSRC and Rolls-Royce plc for funding this programme through a CASE studentship for KI.

REFERENCES

1. T.-W.Chou and T.Ishikawa, Analysis and modelling of two-dimensional fabric composites., *Textile Structural Composites*, Elsevier, Ed.T.-W.Chou and F.K.Ko, 209-264, (1989)
2. T.Ishikawa and T.-W.Chou, Stiffness and Strength behaviour of woven fabric composites., *J. Mater. Sci.* 17, 3211-3220 (1982)
3. N.K.Naik and P.S.Shembekar, Elastic behaviour of woven fabric composites: I - lamina analysis., *J. Comp. Mat.* 26(15), 2196-2225 (1992)
4. P.S.Shembekar and N.K.Naik, Elastic behaviour of woven fabric composites: II - laminate analysis., *J. Comp. Mat.* 26(15), 2226-2246 (1992)

5. N.K.Naik and P.S.Shembekar, Elastic behaviour of woven fabric composites: III - laminate design., *J. Comp. Mat.* **26**(17), 2522-2541 (1992)
6. Z.G.Wang, C.Laird, Z.Hashin, B.W.Rosen, and C.F.Yen, Mechanical behaviour of a cross-weave ceramic matrix composite Part 1 - Tensile and compressive loading., *J. Mater. Sci.* **26**, 4751-4758 (1991)
7. Z.G.Wang, C.Laird, Z.Hashin, B.W.Rosen, and C.F.Yen, Mechanical behaviour of a cross-weave ceramic matrix composite Part 2 - Repeated loading., *J. Mater. Sci.* **26**, 5335-5341 (1991)
8. D.S.Beyerle, S.M.Spearing and A.G.Evans, Damage mechanisms and the mechanical properties of a laminated 0/90 CMC, *J.Am.Ceram. Soc.* **75**(12), 3321-3330 (1992)
9. P.Karandikar and T.W.Chou, Characterisation and modelling of microcracking and elastic moduli changes in Nicalon/CAS composites. *Comp. Sci. & Tech.* **46**, 253-263 (1993)
10. A.W.Pryce and P.A.Smith, Matrix cracking in crossply ceramic matrix composites under quasi-static and cyclic loading, *Acta Metall. Mater.* **42**(3) 861-870 (1994)

Table 1 Mechanical properties of woven SiC/Pyrex

Architecture		E (GPa)	σ_t (MPa)	ϵ_t (%)	ν_{xy}
PW	224	94.2 (6) SD= 4.89	193 (2)	0.415 (2)	0.20
	D	91.9 (4) SD= 6.14	190 (1)	0.434 (1)	----
SHSW	223	81.0 (3) SD= 12.36	142 (2)	0.342 (2)	----
	B	96.0 (7) SD= 7.05	171 (2)	0.300 (2)	0.19
	C	84.2 (4) SD= 1.79	----	----	----

Note that the values in parentheses are the number of samples, and SD is the standard deviation. The laminate reference code follows the architecture description.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of woven SiC/CAS

Architecture	E (GPa)	σ_t (MPa)	ϵ_t (%)	ν_{xy}
PW	115.8 (6) SD = 18.19	148 (1)	0.57 (1)	0.21
8HSW	140.5 (2) SD = 2.50	125 (1)	0.388 (1)	----

Note that the values in parentheses are the number of samples.

Figure 1 Reflected light photomicrograph of a sectioned as-received PW SiC/Pyrex laminate in a plane parallel to warp tows.

Figure 2 A typical stress-strain curve for a PW SiC/Pyrex composite loaded continuously in quasi-static tension.

Figure 3 The reduced stiffness as a function of applied strain for a PW SiC/Pyrex composite.

Figure 4 The reduced stiffness and the cracking density of a 5HSW SiC/Pyrex composite as a function of applied strain.

Figure 5 Reflected light photomicrograph of a sectioned as-received PW SiC/CAS laminate in a plane parallel to warp tows.

Figure 6 The reduced stiffness and the cracking density of a PW SiC/CAS composite as a function of applied strain.

Figure 7 The reduced stiffness and the cracking density of an 8HSW SiC/CAS composite as a function of applied strain.